

PHYSICS AND MATHEMATICS

ONE WAY TO DERIVE THE FORMULA FOR THE INVERSE MATRIX

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Abstract

This paper discusses an alternative method for the appearance of an inverse matrix. The work used the “reverse” method, that is Assuming knowledge of the final result, innovative approaches were found to find the inverse matrix. A special structure of the “discharged” molecular system was used, which makes it possible to break down a large part of the source system into a smaller method system.

Keywords. inverse matrix, matrix, Cramer's rules, system of equations, algebraic additions.

This paper discusses one of the methods for finding the inverse matrix, the purpose of which is to arouse students' interest in scientific research and to select methods that are effective from a practical point of view.

To find the formula for finding the inverse matrix, consider matrix A , of n th order.

$$A = \begin{pmatrix} a_{11} & a_{12} & \dots & a_{1n} \\ a_{21} & a_{22} & \dots & a_{2n} \\ \cdot & \cdot & \dots & \cdot \\ a_{n1} & a_{n2} & \dots & a_{nn} \end{pmatrix} \quad (1)$$

As we know, for the inverse matrix A^{-1} and the matrix A the following equality must be satisfied

$$AA^{-1} = A^{-1}A = E \quad (2)$$

and also matrix A and the inverse matrix A^{-1} must be square matrices of the same order [1].

Let's assume that the inverse matrix A^{-1} has the form:

$$A^{-1} = \begin{pmatrix} x_{11} & x_{12} & \dots & x_{1n} \\ x_{21} & x_{22} & \dots & x_{2n} \\ \cdot & \cdot & \dots & \cdot \\ x_{n1} & x_{n2} & \dots & x_{nn} \end{pmatrix} \quad (3)$$

where x_{ij} , $i, j = 1, 2, 3$ - unknown elements of the inverse matrix. To find them we use equality (2).

$$AA^{-1} = \begin{pmatrix} a_{11} & a_{12} & \dots & a_{1n} \\ a_{21} & a_{22} & \dots & a_{2n} \\ \cdot & \cdot & \dots & \cdot \\ a_{n1} & a_{n2} & \dots & a_{nn} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} x_{11} & x_{12} & \dots & x_{1n} \\ x_{21} & x_{22} & \dots & x_{2n} \\ \cdot & \cdot & \dots & \cdot \\ x_{n1} & x_{n2} & \dots & x_{nn} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} = E. \quad (4)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 AA^{-1} = & \begin{pmatrix} a_{11}x_{11} + a_{12}x_{21} + \dots + a_{1n}x_{n1} & a_{11}x_{12} + a_{12}x_{22} + \dots + a_{1n}x_{n2} \\ a_{21}x_{11} + a_{22}x_{21} + \dots + a_{2n}x_{n1} & a_{21}x_{12} + a_{22}x_{22} + \dots + a_{2n}x_{n2} \\ \cdot & \cdot & \dots & \cdot \\ a_{n1}x_{11} + a_{n2}x_{21} + \dots + a_{nn}x_{n1} & a_{n1}x_{12} + a_{n2}x_{22} + \dots + a_{nn}x_{n2} \\ \dots & a_{11}x_{1n} + a_{12}x_{2n} + \dots + a_{1n}x_{nn} \\ \dots & a_{21}x_{1n} + a_{22}x_{2n} + \dots + a_{2n}x_{nn} \\ \dots & \cdot & \cdot & \dots & \cdot \\ \dots & a_{n1}x_{1n} + a_{n2}x_{2n} + \dots + a_{nn}x_{nn} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & \dots & 0 \\ \cdot & \cdot & \dots & \cdot \\ 0 & 0 & \dots & 1 \end{pmatrix} = E
 \end{aligned} \tag{5}$$

From here we obtain a system of equations

$$\begin{cases} a_{11}x_{11} + a_{12}x_{21} + \dots + a_{1n}x_{n1} = 1 \\ a_{21}x_{11} + a_{22}x_{21} + \dots + a_{2n}x_{n1} = 0 \\ \cdot & \cdot & \dots & \cdot & \cdot \\ a_{n1}x_{11} + a_{n2}x_{21} + \dots + a_{nn}x_{n1} = 0 \\ a_{11}x_{12} + a_{12}x_{22} + \dots + a_{1n}x_{n2} = 0 \\ a_{21}x_{12} + a_{22}x_{22} + \dots + a_{2n}x_{n2} = 1 \\ \cdot & \cdot & \dots & \cdot & \cdot \\ a_{n1}x_{12} + a_{n2}x_{22} + \dots + a_{nn}x_{n2} = 0 \\ \cdot & \cdot & \dots & \cdot & \cdot \\ a_{11}x_{1n} + a_{12}x_{2n} + \dots + a_{1n}x_{nn} = 0 \\ a_{21}x_{1n} + a_{22}x_{2n} + \dots + a_{2n}x_{nn} = 0 \\ \cdot & \cdot & \dots & \cdot & \cdot \\ a_{n1}x_{1n} + a_{n2}x_{2n} + \dots + a_{nn}x_{nn} = 1 \end{cases} \tag{6}$$

Since the first n equations depend on $x_{11}, x_{21}, \dots, x_{n1}$, the next n equations on $x_{12}, x_{22}, \dots, x_{n2}$, and the last n equations depend on $x_{1n}, x_{2n}, \dots, x_{nn}$, it can be written separately as the following system of equations [2]

$$\begin{cases} a_{11}x_{11} + a_{12}x_{21} + \dots + a_{1n}x_{n1} = 1 \\ a_{21}x_{11} + a_{22}x_{21} + \dots + a_{2n}x_{n1} = 0 \\ \cdot & \cdot & \dots & \cdot & \cdot \\ a_{n1}x_{11} + a_{n2}x_{21} + \dots + a_{nn}x_{n1} = 0 \end{cases} \tag{7}$$

$$\begin{cases} a_{11}x_{12} + a_{12}x_{22} + \dots + a_{1n}x_{n2} = 0 \\ a_{21}x_{12} + a_{22}x_{22} + \dots + a_{2n}x_{n2} = 1 \\ \cdot \quad \quad \quad \dots \quad \quad \quad \cdot \quad \quad \quad \cdot \\ a_{n1}x_{12} + a_{n2}x_{22} + \dots + a_{nn}x_{n2} = 0 \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

$$\begin{cases} a_{11}x_{1n} + a_{12}x_{2n} + \dots + a_{1n}x_{nn} = 0 \\ a_{21}x_{1n} + a_{22}x_{2n} + \dots + a_{2n}x_{nn} = 0 \\ \cdot \quad \quad \quad \dots \quad \quad \quad \cdot \quad \quad \quad \cdot \\ a_{n1}x_{1n} + a_{n2}x_{2n} + \dots + a_{nn}x_{nn} = 1 \end{cases} \quad (9)$$

The solution to these systems of equations is found using Cramer's rule. If

$$\Delta(A) = \begin{vmatrix} a_{11} & a_{12} & \dots & a_{1n} \\ a_{21} & a_{22} & \dots & a_{2n} \\ \cdot & \cdot & \dots & \cdot \\ a_{n1} & a_{n2} & \dots & a_{nn} \end{vmatrix}$$

is the determinant of the matrix A, then for system (7) we have [3]

$$\Delta(A) \cdot x_{11} = \begin{vmatrix} 1 & a_{12} & \dots & a_{1n} \\ 0 & a_{22} & \dots & a_{2n} \\ \cdot & \cdot & \dots & \cdot \\ 0 & a_{n2} & \dots & a_{nn} \end{vmatrix} = A_{11} \quad \Delta(A) \cdot x_{21} = \begin{vmatrix} a_{11} & 1 & \dots & a_{1n} \\ a_{21} & 0 & \dots & a_{2n} \\ \cdot & \cdot & \dots & \cdot \\ a_{n1} & 0 & \dots & a_{nn} \end{vmatrix} = A_{12}$$

$$\dots \quad \Delta(A) \cdot x_{n1} = \begin{vmatrix} a_{11} & a_{12} & \dots & 1 \\ a_{21} & a_{22} & \dots & 0 \\ \cdot & \cdot & \dots & \cdot \\ a_{n1} & a_{n2} & \dots & 0 \end{vmatrix} = A_{1n}$$

and for system (8): [4]

$$\Delta(A) \cdot x_{12} = \begin{vmatrix} 0 & a_{12} & \dots & a_{1n} \\ 1 & a_{22} & \dots & a_{2n} \\ \cdot & \cdot & \dots & \cdot \\ 0 & a_{n2} & \dots & a_{nn} \end{vmatrix} = A_{21} \quad \Delta(A) \cdot x_{22} = \begin{vmatrix} a_{11} & 0 & \dots & a_{1n} \\ a_{21} & 1 & \dots & a_{2n} \\ \cdot & \cdot & \dots & \cdot \\ a_{n1} & 0 & \dots & a_{nn} \end{vmatrix} = A_{22}$$

$$\dots \quad \Delta(A) \cdot x_{n2} = \begin{vmatrix} a_{11} & a_{12} & \dots & 0 \\ a_{21} & a_{22} & \dots & 1 \\ \cdot & \cdot & \dots & \cdot \\ a_{n1} & a_{n2} & \dots & 0 \end{vmatrix} = A_{2n}$$

and for system (9):

$$\Delta(A) \cdot x_{1n} = \begin{vmatrix} 0 & a_{12} & \dots & a_{1n} \\ 0 & a_{22} & \dots & a_{2n} \\ \cdot & \cdot & \dots & \cdot \\ 1 & a_{n2} & \dots & a_{nn} \end{vmatrix} = A_{n1} \quad \Delta(A) \cdot x_{2n} = \begin{vmatrix} a_{11} & 0 & \dots & a_{1n} \\ a_{21} & 0 & \dots & a_{2n} \\ \cdot & \cdot & \dots & \cdot \\ a_{n1} & 1 & \dots & a_{nn} \end{vmatrix} = A_{n2}$$

$$\dots \quad \Delta(A) \cdot x_{nn} = \begin{vmatrix} a_{11} & a_{12} & \dots & 0 \\ a_{21} & a_{22} & \dots & 0 \\ \cdot & \cdot & \dots & \cdot \\ a_{n1} & a_{n2} & \dots & 1 \end{vmatrix} = A_{nn}$$

where A_{ij} , $i, j = 1, n$ - algebraic complements of the matrix A .

If the determinant of the matrix A is not equal to zero, i.e. $\Delta(A) \neq 0$, then [5]

$$\begin{aligned} x_{11} &= \frac{1}{\Delta(A)} A_{11} & x_{12} &= \frac{1}{\Delta(A)} A_{21} & \dots & x_{1n} &= \frac{1}{\Delta(A)} A_{n1} \\ x_{21} &= \frac{1}{\Delta(A)} A_{12} & x_{22} &= \frac{1}{\Delta(A)} A_{22} & \dots & x_{2n} &= \frac{1}{\Delta(A)} A_{n2} \\ &\dots & &\dots & & & \\ x_{n1} &= \frac{1}{\Delta(A)} A_{1n} & x_{n2} &= \frac{1}{\Delta(A)} A_{2n} & \dots & x_{nn} &= \frac{1}{\Delta(A)} A_{nn} \end{aligned}$$

From here, putting (3) we get [6]

$$A^{-1} = \frac{1}{\Delta(A)} \begin{pmatrix} A_{11} & A_{21} & \dots & A_{n1} \\ A_{12} & A_{22} & \dots & A_{n2} \\ \cdot & \cdot & \dots & \cdot \\ A_{1n} & A_{2n} & \dots & A_{nn} \end{pmatrix} \quad (10)$$

So, we found the inverse matrix. For any non-singular matrix one can find the inverse matrix.

Conclusion. This article provides one of the methods for finding the inverse matrix, for those students who are interested in doing scientific research.

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